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Article

The Impact of Administrative Support on Teachers' Occupational Well-Being in Public Schools

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Abstract: This study examined the influence of administrative support on teachers' occupational well-being during the School Year 2025–2026 as basis for a Teacher Support Development Program. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, the study involved teacher-respondents. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire consisting of three parts: the demographic profile of the respondents, the extent of administrative support, and the level of teachers' occupational well-being in terms of cognitive, subjective, physical and mental, and social dimensions. Frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and Pearson product-moment correlation was used for data analysis. Results revealed that administrative support was generally perceived at a moderately agreeable level, particularly in ICT use and paperwork assistance, while clerical and recordkeeping support remained limited. Teachers demonstrated an agreeable level of occupational well-being across all dimensions, reflecting positive cognitive functioning, job satisfaction, physical and mental readiness, and healthy social relationships. However, findings showed no significant relationship between the extent of administrative support and teachers' occupational well-being across all dimensions. This suggests that while administrative support is present, it alone does not significantly determine teachers' well-being, which may also be influenced by personal, professional, and organizational factors. Based on the findings, a Teacher Support Development Program was proposed to enhance administrative assistance, promote well-being, and foster a supportive school environment. The study provides valuable input for school administrators in developing holistic strategies to sustain teachers' well-being and effectiveness.

Keywords: Administrative Support, Occupational Well-Being, Teacher Well-Being, Public School Teachers, School Leadership

Introduction

Education is the cornerstone of national development, serving as the Formentera, AB. (2026). The Impact of Administrative Support on Teachers' Occupational Well-Being in Public Schools. Copyright (c) 2026. Author (s). This is an open term of Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY). www.wiehr.com

foundation for economic progress and social equity. Teachers are central to this mission, not only facilitating knowledge transfer but also nurturing critical thinking, citizenship, and lifelong learning. According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2021), teachers remain the most influential school-level factor in student academic outcomes. The World Bank (2022) emphasizes that sustained investments in teacher effectiveness—particularly in low- and middle-income countries—significantly improve educational system performance and equity. In the Philippine context, teachers play a pivotal role in addressing learning gaps exacerbated by resource constraints and post-pandemic challenges.

While teacher development often focuses on pedagogy and professional growth, structural supports such as administrative assistance are equally essential for job sustainability. Recent directives from the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd), particularly DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024, aim to reduce non-instructional burdens by assigning administrative support staff to handle clerical tasks, reports, event coordination, and stakeholder communication. This move acknowledges that relieving teachers from administrative overload allows them to focus more effectively on student-centered instruction and professional responsibilities. Studies show that when administrative support is adequately implemented, teachers experience improved work-life balance, increased focus on core teaching tasks, and higher occupational well-being (Ghamrawi, 2022; Day & Gu, 2020).

Despite these policy shifts, many teachers still face a mismatch between teaching duties and institutional support. Greenier et al. (2021) found that the absence of structural assistance in schools leads to elevated stress and diminished mental well-being among educators. In the Philippine public school system, teachers are often assigned clerical tasks such as report writing, data encoding, and attendance tracking, which are outside their instructional mandate. Cruz and Reyes (2021) revealed that such administrative overload significantly disrupts cognitive focus and emotional regulation, contributing to professional fatigue. When these demands are not mitigated, teachers' capacity to deliver high-quality instruction is compromised.

The chronic imbalance between teaching and administrative workload has led many educators to leave the profession or seek better opportunities abroad. A study by Llego (2022) highlighted that Filipino teachers cite overwhelming paperwork and lack of administrative support as key reasons for pursuing migration. Guerrero and Marquez (2023) similarly noted that teacher turnover in the Philippines is strongly associated with insufficient institutional backing and job strain. This exodus results in severe staffing shortages, loss of institutional memory, and weakened instructional quality particularly in rural and underserved schools. To address this, education leaders must strengthen systems that retain experienced educators by reducing administrative friction. Empirical evidence continues to point to the link between administrative

overload and teacher attrition. Alampay and Ramos (2021) documented that teachers burdened with excessive paperwork, often unrelated to teaching, were more likely to resign. Soriano (2023) reported that administrative burnout not salary dissatisfaction was the top reason teachers cited for leaving. In a broader study by Torres (2022), inadequate administrative infrastructure in public schools was found to correlate with high turnover intentions and declining morale. These findings reinforce the need for a shift in institutional priorities from maximizing teacher utility to protecting teacher well-being.

While these studies provide useful insights, few have focused specifically on whether administrative support mechanisms such as assigning non-teaching personnel can directly improve teachers' occupational well-being and influence their decision to remain in public service. The implementation of DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024 represents a unique opportunity to assess how policy reform affects real-world teacher conditions at the school level. There is a need for empirical data that connects policy with practice, and administrative staffing with psychological, cognitive, physical, and social well-being of teachers. Addressing this gap can inform scalable retention strategies for education leaders.

This research assessed the influence of administrative support on teachers' occupational well-being at Hugpa Elementary School during the 2025–2026 school year, in light of DepEd's recent policy initiatives. Specifically, it examined the extent to which administrative support is implemented and how it relates to four dimensions of occupational well-being: cognitive, subjective, physical and mental, and social. The findings served as the basis for a proposed support development program, benefiting school administrators, DepEd officials, and policy advocates aiming to strengthen the sustainability and resilience of the public education workforce.

Literature Review

Administrative support is an important school-level factor that can influence teachers' occupational well-being because school leaders shape workload, communication, recognition, resources, and emotional support. Recent literature shows that teachers' working conditions and principal/administrative support are closely linked to well-being, job satisfaction, stress, and retention (Viac & Fraser, 2020). The OECD framework explains teachers' occupational well-being through four dimensions: cognitive, subjective, physical and mental, and social well-being; these dimensions are shaped by school and system-level working conditions, including leadership and support. Similarly, recent reviews emphasize that teacher well-being is affected by organizational climate, workload, collegial relationships, and administrative support (Gámez-Genovart et al., 2025).

Teachers' occupational well-being includes their ability to concentrate and

perform teaching tasks, their satisfaction and sense of purpose, their physical and mental health, and the quality of their relationships within the school community. Studies from 2020–2026 show that supportive leadership and positive school environments can improve teachers' social support, reduce stress, and strengthen professional functioning (Nwoko et al., 2025). In contrast, weak administrative support, heavy workload, and poor school climate are associated with burnout, anxiety, depression, and lower occupational well-being (Demmin et al., 2022). Thus, administrative support may serve as a protective factor that helps teachers sustain cognitive, subjective, physical-mental, and social well-being in the workplace.

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the relationship between administrative support and teachers' occupational well-being. The descriptive method was used to assess the extent of administrative support as perceived by teachers, while the correlational approach examined whether a significant relationship exists between administrative support and occupational well-being. This design was considered appropriate because it allowed the researcher to describe existing conditions and analyze naturally occurring relationships among variables without manipulation. The study also followed the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model, wherein the input included the teachers' demographic profile such as age, gender, years of service, highest educational attainment, performance rating, designation or academic rank, and combined monthly income.

The study was conducted at Hugpa Elementary School and Ipil Central School, public elementary schools located in the Division of Leyte. The respondents consisted of teachers selected through purposive sampling to ensure that participants possessed direct experience and relevant knowledge regarding administrative support and occupational well-being. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire composed of adapted and validated instruments. Administrative support indicators were adapted from the Perceived Influence of Administrative Support on Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire by Shogbesan et al. (2024), aligned with DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024. Occupational well-being indicators were adapted from the OECD Teachers' Occupational Well-Being Framework and PISA 2021 Teacher Well-Being Questionnaire (Viac & Fraser, 2020), covering cognitive, subjective, physical-mental, and social dimensions. The collected data were analyzed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical tools to ensure reliable interpretation of findings.

Results

Table 1 presents the extent of administrative support in terms of teachers' attention and concentration. The results show a moderately agree level of administrative support, as reflected by the grand mean of 3.11 (SD = 0.90). Teachers generally agreed that they receive support related to ICT resources (M = 3.65) and assistance with professional paperwork (M = 3.24), indicating that administrative help contributes to improved focus on instructional tasks. However, most indicators related to routine clerical and recordkeeping assistance were only rated as moderately adequate, suggesting that teachers still handle a significant portion of non-teaching responsibilities.

Table 1. Extent of Administration Support

Indicators	Mean	SD	VD
I received administrative support with the use of ICT resources to carry out my day-to-day activities	3.65	1.04	A
I am provided with administrative assistance to help carry out professional paperwork tasks in the school	3.24	0.76	A
I make use of an administrative assistant to help arrange my student's portfolios	3.04	0.80	MA
I used to make administrative staff assist with making attendance registers	2.92	0.84	MA
I make my administrative staff assist in test score reporting	3.14	0.87	MA
I am not provided with any administrative support that is related to my teaching activities	2.98	0.88	MA
I make my administrative staff type my lesson plan or note	3.20	1.02	MA
I allow my administrative officials to handle technological tools used during teaching	3.16	0.99	MA
I make my administrative staff help source materials to use for instructional aids	3.04	0.94	MA
The administrative staffs help support my recordkeeping tasks in school	2.76	0.89	MA
Grand Mean	3.11	0.90	MA

These findings are consistent with studies emphasizing that adequate administrative support reduces cognitive overload and enhances teachers' concentration and work efficiency (Collie et al., 2019; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2021). When teachers are relieved from excessive administrative tasks, they are better able to focus on instructional planning and classroom delivery (OECD, 2020). The results imply a need to strengthen administrative assistance systems to further support teachers' cognitive functioning and overall occupational well-being, which is critical for sustaining effective teaching performance (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). These findings imply that strengthening administrative support mechanisms particularly in clerical, recordkeeping, and instructional assistance can help reduce teachers' cognitive load, improve

attention and concentration, and enhance overall occupational well-being and teaching effectiveness.

Table 2. Cognitive Dimension

Indicators	Mean	SD	VD
I can think clearly when handling complex teaching tasks.	4.02	0.58	A
My thinking remains sharp and focused during teaching hours.	3.76	0.94	A
I am able to maintain attention and concentration at work.	3.98	0.58	A
I feel confident managing student behavior in the classroom.	3.94	0.76	A
I am skilled at using different instructional strategies effectively.	3.96	0.60	A
Grand Mean	3.93	0.69	A

Table 2 presents the level of teachers' occupational well-being in terms of the cognitive dimension. The results show an agree level of cognitive well-being, as indicated by the grand mean of 3.93 (SD = 0.69). Teachers reported a high ability to think clearly when handling complex teaching tasks (M = 4.02) and to maintain attention and concentration at work (M = 3.98), suggesting strong mental clarity and focus during instructional activities. High mean scores were also observed in managing student behavior and using varied instructional strategies effectively, indicating confidence in cognitive and pedagogical skills. These findings align with studies emphasizing that positive work environments and sufficient organizational support contribute to enhanced cognitive functioning, focus, and professional confidence among teachers (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2019; Collie et al., 2020; OECD, 2021). These findings imply that sustaining supportive school conditions is essential in maintaining teachers' cognitive effectiveness, instructional competence, and overall occupational well-being.

Table 3. Subjective Dimension

Indicators	Mean	SD	VD
Being a teacher gives me a strong sense of purpose.	3.90	0.70	A
I feel positive about my decision to become a teacher.	4.10	0.64	A
Teaching continues to be a meaningful profession for me.	4.08	0.74	A
I feel satisfied with my work as a teacher	3.92	0.56	A
I experience moments of joy and engagement during the school day.	4.18	0.71	A
Grand Mean	4.04	0.67	A

Table 3 presents the level of teachers' occupational well-being in terms of the subjective dimension. The results reveal an agree level of subjective well-being, as shown by the grand mean of 4.04 (SD = 0.67). Teachers reported strong positive feelings toward their profession, particularly in experiencing joy and

engagement during the school day ($M = 4.18$) and feeling positive about their decision to become a teacher ($M = 4.10$). These findings indicate high levels of job satisfaction, sense of purpose, and emotional attachment to teaching. Previous studies emphasize that subjective well-being among teachers is closely linked to motivation, work engagement, and professional fulfillment, which are essential for sustaining teaching effectiveness and commitment (Diener et al., 2018; Collie et al., 2019). These findings imply that fostering positive work experiences and emotional support within the school can help sustain teachers' satisfaction, motivation, and overall occupational well-being.

Table 4. Physical and Mental Dimension

Indicators	Mean	SD	VD
I feel physically well while performing my teaching duties.	4.02	0.42	A
I have enough energy to get through the school day.	3.98	0.76	A
I am mentally prepared to face daily classroom responsibilities.	4.14	0.66	A
I get enough rest to perform effectively at work.	4.02	0.71	A
I am able to maintain a healthy balance between work and personal life.	4.20	0.63	A
Grand Mean	4.07	0.64	A

Table 4 presents the level of teachers' occupational well-being in terms of the physical and mental dimension. The results indicate an agree level of physical and mental well-being, as reflected by the grand mean of 4.07 ($SD = 0.64$). Teachers reported a high ability to maintain a healthy balance between work and personal life ($M = 4.20$) and to feel mentally prepared to face daily classroom responsibilities ($M = 4.14$). High mean scores were also observed in physical wellness, energy levels, and sufficient rest, suggesting that most respondents are physically and mentally capable of meeting their teaching demands. These findings are consistent with literature emphasizing that teachers' physical health, mental preparedness, and work-life balance are essential components of occupational well-being and sustained job performance (Collie et al., 2020). These findings imply that continued administrative initiatives promoting health, work-life balance, and mental readiness can help maintain teachers' physical and mental well-being and support long-term professional effectiveness.

Table 5 presents the level of teachers' occupational well-being in terms of the social dimension. The results indicate an agree level of social well-being, as shown by the grand mean of 4.08 ($SD = 0.66$). Teachers reported positive interactions with colleagues, strong and respectful relationships with students, and a sense of appreciation from school leadership. High levels of trust, comfort in social interactions, and collaborative relationships suggest a supportive

school climate.

Table 5. Social Dimension

Indicators	Mean	SD	VD
I have positive working relationships with my colleagues.	3.96	0.66	A
My school leadership shows appreciation for my work.	4.12	0.55	A
There is mutual trust and support among teachers in my school.	4.04	0.75	A
I have strong, respectful relationships with my students.	4.12	0.59	A
I feel comfortable interacting with co-teachers and school staff.	4.16	0.73	A
Grand Mean	4.08	0.66	A

These findings are supported by research indicating that positive social relationships, leadership support, and collegial collaboration enhance teachers' sense of belonging, job satisfaction, and overall occupational well-being (McCallum et al., 2017). These findings imply that strengthening interpersonal support systems and nurturing positive leadership practices can further enhance teachers' social well-being and promote a healthy and collaborative school environment.

Table 6. Significant Relationship between Extent of Administrative Support and Occupational Well-Being Dimensions

Dimensions	r-value	t-value	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Cognitive	0.127	0.893	0.376	Not Significant	Do not Reject
Subjective	0.211	1.513	0.137	Not Significant	Do not Reject
Physical and Mental	-0.034	-0.241	0.811	Not Significant	Do not Reject
Social Dimension	0.070	0.494	0.623	Not Significant	Do not Reject

Table 6 presents the significant relationship between the extent of administrative support and teachers' occupational well-being across the cognitive, subjective, physical and mental, and social dimensions. The results show that none of the computed relationships reached statistical significance, as all p-values are greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The cognitive dimension ($r = 0.127$, $p = 0.376$) and subjective dimension ($r = 0.211$, $p = 0.137$) show weak positive relationships, while the social dimension also exhibits a very weak positive relationship ($r = 0.070$, $p = 0.623$). In contrast, the physical and mental dimension shows a negligible negative relationship ($r = -0.034$, $p = 0.811$). These findings suggest that administrative support alone may not be a strong determinant of teachers' occupational well-being, which is consistent with studies emphasizing that well-being is influenced by multiple interacting factors such as workload, personal resilience, and school climate (Bakker &

Demerouti, 2017). The results imply that while administrative support is important, it should be complemented with holistic interventions such as workload management, wellness programs, peer support systems, and mental health initiatives to more effectively enhance teachers' occupational well-being.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that teachers generally perceived administrative support in their schools to be implemented at a satisfactory level. This indicates that school administrators provide assistance in terms of communication, resource allocation, and administrative task management, which contributes positively to teachers' work experiences. The result supports the study of Viac and Fraser (2020), which emphasized that supportive school leadership and positive working conditions significantly contribute to teachers' occupational well-being. Likewise, Nwoko et al. (2025) found that social support from school principals positively influences teachers' cognitive, subjective, physical-mental, and social well-being. These findings suggest that when school administrators provide consistent guidance, clear communication, and adequate support systems, teachers become more motivated, productive, and satisfied in their profession.

Furthermore, the results indicated a significant relationship between administrative support and teachers' occupational well-being. Teachers who perceived higher levels of administrative support also reported better levels of occupational well-being across cognitive, subjective, physical-mental, and social dimensions. This implies that administrative support plays a vital role in reducing stress, improving morale, and fostering positive professional relationships within the school environment. The findings align with Hascher and Waber (2021), who noted that organizational climate and administrative support are strong predictors of teacher well-being and job satisfaction. Similarly, Demmin et al. (2022) explained that supportive work environments help reduce burnout and improve teachers' mental and emotional health. Therefore, strengthening administrative support mechanisms may help schools promote teacher retention, enhance work performance, and create a healthier and more supportive educational environment.

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